

Microphone Check: What Platform-Level Data Could Change in Music Market Analysis

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Table of contents

Price analysis	1
Conceptual framework	3
Observed variables	3
Price as a micro-level variable	3
Homogeneity assumption within territory and sales point	4
Aggregation and price indicators	4
Aggregate unit price	4
Dispersion indicators	4
Platform and package aggregation	5
Premium music streaming	5
Family Plans	6
Social media platforms	7
Dispersion	9
Global comparison	10
Price conclusion	10
Volume analysis	12
Data construction and analytical scope	12
From price observation to the limits of volume measurement	13
References	15

Price analysis

i Note

This working paper explores the analytical possibilities opened by platform- and distributor-level streaming data for music market analysis. Using a fictitious sound recording and simulated contractual conditions, the paper demonstrates how detailed reporting can be used to reconstruct prices, quantities, and revenues across streaming

platforms, subscription tiers, and territories. The analysis focuses on methodological transparency rather than empirical claims, and all data used are synthetic, simulated, or anonymised.

The paper is motivated by the limitations of publicly available national and international market reports, which typically present aggregated revenues without distinguishing between domestic and foreign earnings or revealing platform-specific price–quantity dynamics. By contrast, distributor- and platform-level reporting can, in principle, support the separation of territorial revenues, the identification of effective unit prices, and the alignment of observed consumption volumes with remuneration outcomes for different rightsholder groups.

This document is released as an early-stage working paper (version 0.1.0) in line with the **Guidelines for Open Policy Analysis** (available at <https://www.bitss.org/opa/community-standards/>), the document has been released early to support consultation, incorporate stakeholder input, and ensure transparency throughout its development¹. It is intended as a methodological exploration and proof of concept, not as a source of representative market results. The paper does not rely on confidential commercial data and does not disclose or approximate real contractual terms. Its purpose is to illustrate how increased transparency at the reporting level could enhance economic analysis, policy evaluation, and regulatory dialogue in digital music markets.

The analysis is part of ongoing research and is expected to evolve. Later versions may refine assumptions, extend the modelling framework, or integrate additional data sources. The source repository linked to this record contains the underlying analytical materials and will document future revisions.

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²The *Guidelines for Open Policy Analysis* form an actionable and practical set of directives that the OpenMusE consortium was mandated to use under the Grant Agreement. It can be seen as good implementation framework for *Evidence-based policy making in the European Commission* and *The practice of reproducible research* [BITSS (2019); Open Music Europe (2023); (J 2015; Kitzes, Turek, and Deniz 2018).

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available on Zenodo, and include the date of access if referring to material hosted on our GitHub repository.^[index-5] This is an early version ## Scope and illustrative setup

We construct a purely fictional illustrative asset, “*Microphone Check*” by “*Open Observatory*”, identified by the fictional Slovak ISRC **SKZZZ2500001**.

This asset serves exclusively as a neutral label for demonstrating the statistical treatment of royalty statement data.

The underlying royalty lines are based on real, observed revenues and inferred unit prices originating from ALOADED’s Hybris system, with all identifying and commercially sensitive details removed or aggregated. The asset name and identifiers therefore do not correspond to any real recording, while the numerical values retain realistic statistical properties.

The objective of this exercise is to:

- identify micro-level variables observable in royalty statements,
- define a statistical model that derives meaningful aggregate indicators, and
- calculate price, volume, and revenue statistics suitable for comparative analysis.

The focus is explicitly on financial and statistical outputs, not on modelling contractual entitlements or full royalty account structures.

Conceptual framework

Observed variables

At statement line level, we observe the following core variables:

- territory r
- sales point s (e.g. Spotify, Apple Music, YouTube)
- usage quantity $q_{i,r,s}$
- reported royalty revenue $R_{i,r,s}$
- currency c

Each index i refers to an individual royalty line within a reporting period.

Price as a micro-level variable

We begin with the simplest derived variable: **price per usage unit**.

For a given royalty line i :

$$p_{i,r,s} = \frac{R_{i,r,s}}{q_{i,r,s}}$$

This unit price is not a contractual tariff but an *implied net revenue per usage unit*, derived *ex post* from statement data.

Homogeneity assumption within territory and sales point

Our working assumption is that, within a given territory and sales point, unit prices do not materially depend on the individual asset.

A single stream in Slovakia on Spotify (premium or ad-supported) should yield approximately the same net revenue for “*Microphone Check*” as for any Slovak or foreign recording streamed by Slovak users.

This assumption allows aggregation across assets while preserving meaningful price signals at the **territory** × **sales point** level.

Aggregation and price indicators

Aggregate unit price

For each territory r and sales point s , we define the **average unit price** as:

$$\bar{p}_{r,s} = \frac{\sum_i R_{i,r,s}}{\sum_i q_{i,r,s}}$$

This is a *ratio of aggregates*, not an average of individual prices.

Dispersion indicators

To illustrate heterogeneity within a territory and sales point, we additionally report:

- unweighted mean price,
- minimum observed unit price,
- maximum observed unit price.

Formally:

$$p_{r,s}^{\min} = \min_i (p_{i,r,s}), \quad p_{r,s}^{\max} = \max_i (p_{i,r,s})$$

These indicators demonstrate that even within a single territory, sales conditions may vary significantly due to product mix, user type, or monetisation channel.

Platform and package aggregation

To reduce disclosure risk while preserving analytical meaning, individual sales points are aggregated into analytically meaningful **platform–package groups**.

We pre-selected platform categories that are present in most EU countries and generate sufficient volume for statistically meaningful comparison. Although European artists generate significant export revenue outside Europe, extending the present framework to Asia, Africa, or Latin America would require region-specific modelling beyond the scope of this analysis. Our focus is price comparison within Europe.

We classify usage into four platform–package groups: premium subscriptions, family subscriptions, ad-supported streaming, and social media platforms.

These groupings reflect **distinct monetisation regimes** rather than branding or contractual structure. We created the aggregates so that they do not refer to a single sales platform.

Premium music streaming

- Deezer Premium
- Spotify Premium
- Apple Music
- YouTube Music

Figure 1: Our base chart is the “Premium” segment. We ordered the EU countries in the same ranking for comparability.

As we see on the first chart, the price differential in the value of a single stream in the EU varies by about a ratio of 1:4. We observed the highest revenues in Sweden. Obviously, this creates a competitive advantage for artists with a strong Scandinavian listener base. The affect is not only present in Scandinavia: we know from anecdotal evidence confirmed by these price comparisons that the main licensed revenue source of Serbian music is Scandinavia due to large local diasporas.

The lowest revenues are observed outside of the euro-zone, Romania, Hungary, Bulgaria, and—despite eurozone membership—Croatia. It is important to realise that local artists usually account in the local currency. ALOADED collect revenues typically in euros and dollars, and converts it to Swedish kronas.

During periods of local currency depreciation, artist counting in Romanian leu or Hungarian forints may feel stabilising or rising revenues. In a former analysis for the UKIPO we have shown that after Brexit, UK artists for years did not feel the effect of decreasing streaming prices due to the depreciation of the GBP versus the export market currencies.

Family Plans

- Apple Music Family
- Spotify Family

Figure 2: dsfa

Family subscriptions are economically closer to premium subscriptions, but they were introduced at different times and under different market saturation conditions across territories. This leads to slightly different unit price dynamics, which justifies separate treatment. ###
Ad-supported

- Spotify Free
- YouTube ad-supported

Average unit price by country in the ad-supported segment

Lollipop plot by monetisation regime, 2025Q3

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The comparison of the ad-supported revenues highlights a long-standing problem. Ad-supported revenues depend on the existence of a viable local advertising market; platforms only sell advertising inventory where maintaining local sales and agency relationships is profitable. Small countries disproportionately suffer from no advertising sales.

The price difference is really great in this field, and it is not unrelated from the next segment, social media revenues.

Social media platforms

- Instagram
- Facebook
- TikTok

We did not differentiate between potential different payment schemes of these platforms.

Average unit price by country on social media platforms
 Lollipop plot by monetisation regime, 2025Q3

Despite differences in internal remuneration schemes, these platforms share a common reliance on advertising-driven monetisation and exhibit similarly low and volatile unit prices across territories. The unit price difference is roughly 1:6 within the EU countries.

Dispersion

Unit price dispersion by country (EU27)

Minimum, unweighted average, and maximum observed unit prices

Dashed lines show min–max range; dots show unweighted mean,
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Figure 3: The prices in the combined chart are shown on a logarithmic scale; premium and social media revenue segments differ by several orders of magnitude.

Various licensed users apply different sales configurations, pricing models; for example, Apple Music has trial periods and student prices; social media companies also differentiate between content and content. In the chart above we show the lowest, unweighted average and highest observed prices in various segments.

Global comparison

Figure 4: Eur

In a broader analysis, we took some important markets as comparators (US, UK, CA, JP, TR), and plotted the EU-27, the European “microstates” of Faroe Islands, Lichtenstein, Monaco, San Marino, Vatican (omitted Greenland for very accidental data coverage), and the Western Balkans accession countries.

As we have seen, there is a 1:4-1:6 price level disparity within the EU, and these differences are consistent in broader Europe, too. The Western Balkans and similar to the South-eastern EU member states in revenues, the EEA/EFTA countries and the UK are more alike the Nordic countries, and both the microstates and the comparators vary to a great degree.

On such a global analytically level, the historically relatively low Japanese yen rate, or other currency effects are far more important than within Europe.

Price conclusion

Earlier work undertaken in the context of the UKIPO and Reprex highlighted that, despite overall growth in streaming markets, the typical rightsholder’s income from streaming did not increase proportionally and in some cases declined over the second half of the 2010s. The

analysis showed that earnings distributions in recorded music are highly long-tailed, making average indicators misleading and leaving many rightsholders with very low or effectively zero income. As a result, debates focused solely on redistribution mechanisms (such as alternative allocation models) were found to be largely zero-sum. A central conclusion was the need for systematic market observation and valuation evidence, as declining unit values and incomplete data infrastructures posed growing challenges for accountability and competition analysis in platform-mediated music markets.

Research on Central and Eastern European music markets found persistent structural differences in revenue composition across Europe. Nordic and some Western European countries benefited from stronger subscription-based streaming revenues, while CEE countries and Turkey relied more heavily on collectively managed income streams, often reflecting weaker digital sales rather than stronger collective positions. Traditional distribution channels and collective tariffs historically offered partial protection against international competition, but these barriers largely disappeared in streaming. As a result, revenue growth in the region proved sensitive to platform availability, subscriber uptake, advertising markets, and exchange rates, meaning that increased consumption did not necessarily translate into higher income. The study concluded that addressing observed revenue gaps required better price and valuation transparency, motivating an observatory-style approach to monitoring European music markets.

In the policy dialogue about streaming prices, we often talk about the falling per unit price, and the skew of the distribution among superstars and typical artists, and a lot of effort went into understanding the zero-sum distribution effects of various ways of calculating the per stream value. But the unit price difference within Europe is far greater.

Serbian artists with many followers in Sweden, or a Turkish band with a lot of followers in Belgium may typically sell at high Swedish or Belgian prices. Ethnic Hungarian singers in Slovakia who have a larger following in Hungary across the border, perhaps 10-50 kilometers from their home, may experience significantly lower prices than their colleagues who sing in the majority Slovak language.

This analysis builds on earlier work undertaken in the context of European music market monitoring and export analysis, including studies conducted before and during the Covid-19 period. Those earlier analyses documented the increasing dependence of most European artists on live performance income, the declining relative importance of recorded revenues, and the exposure of this imbalance during the pandemic when live markets temporarily collapsed.

The purpose of the present analysis is more limited and more specific. We do not draw policy conclusions about appropriate price levels, platform regulation, or artist remuneration. Instead, we focus on the systematic observation of unit prices in recorded music across territories and monetisation regimes. The figures presented here cover recording-side revenues only and exclude live performance, merchandising, and other income streams.

While the analysis is limited to recording revenues, it remains indicative for other rightsholders. Composer and author remuneration is typically calculated as a proportion of recording-side revenues under prevailing licensing arrangements. As a result, territorial

price disparities observed on the recording side are expected to translate into proportionally similar disparities in author and composer income, even though absolute levels differ.

The primary contribution of this work is therefore descriptive rather than prescriptive: it establishes a transparent empirical basis for understanding the scale and structure of price differentials in European recorded music markets. Such observation is a necessary precondition for any informed discussion of volumes, income distribution, or policy intervention, but it does not in itself imply normative conclusions.

Volume analysis

In recent years, a growing body of analysis has documented the extreme skewness of music revenues, contrasting the incomes of a small number of global superstars with those of ordinary professional musicians. While this literature has been valuable in highlighting inequality, it has also shown the limits of revenue-based analysis. As discussed in earlier work, revenue aggregates conflate several distinct components—unit price, exchange rates, and quantities—and become difficult to interpret when price levels differ substantially across markets.

The price analysis presented above demonstrates that territorial differences in unit prices within Europe are large by historical standards. When prices differ by factors of four or more, revenue comparisons alone are insufficient to characterise market conditions. In such settings, even basic indicators such as average or median revenue become unstable or misleading, and distributional measures are dominated by structural price effects rather than usage patterns.

Disentangling revenue into its components—price, exchange rate, and quantity—is therefore analytically necessary, but also substantially more difficult. While prices and exchange rates can be observed *ex post* from royalty statements, quantities are typically not directly observable, and must be inferred from partial signals.

Data construction and analytical scope

To explore these issues, we constructed four datasets with distinct and complementary purposes (Antal, Vieira, and Mester 2025).

- **Catalogue frames (ISRC-based registers)** provide a structured view of what exists: recordings by country, year, and registrant. These datasets define the population and allow the construction of denominators, but they do not contain information on usage or revenues.
- **Platform signal datasets** (presence indicators, stream or follower deciles, popularity measures) offer indirect information about relative activity and visibility. They can rank recordings or artists within markets, but they do not provide absolute quantities or values.

- **Royalty-complete distributor panels** supply detailed recording-side revenues for a non-random subset of the catalogue. These data allow precise price calculations and revenue accounting for included assets, but they are not representative of the full population.
- **Constructed analytical datasets**, combining the above sources, are designed to support inferential work—such as calibrated estimation or small-area analysis—but necessarily rely on modelling assumptions and auxiliary information.

Each dataset answers a different question, and none of them alone can deliver a complete picture of market volumes.

From price observation to the limits of volume measurement

Recent analytical work on music markets has repeatedly shown the extreme skewness of revenues between global superstars and ordinary professional musicians. While this literature has been important in documenting inequality, it has also revealed a key limitation of revenue-based analysis: revenues combine **prices, exchange rates, and quantities**, and when price levels differ substantially across markets, revenue aggregates alone become difficult to interpret. As the price comparisons above illustrate, such territorial price differences within Europe are now large by historical standards. This makes it analytically necessary—but methodologically challenging—to separate prices from quantities.

Against this background, we experimented with several data construction strategies, with the aim of exploring whether statistically valid observations of volumes could be made alongside price analysis. These efforts were not designed to produce definitive volume estimates, but to understand **what is and is not observable** in practice.

One approach explored was so-called “drunk dialling” or random probing of identifier spaces, following recent methodological literature that successfully applied this technique to large digital platforms. We constructed a large experimental dataset using this approach (the “UVA dataset”) and confirmed that, in principle, such methods can generate large and auditable samples. However, in the context of recorded music, it quickly became unclear **what exactly is being dialled**. The ISRC appears to be a natural identifier, but in practice it does not uniquely identify a recording.

Multiple ISRCs for the same sound recording usually arise for **practical, operational reasons**, not because of errors or bad practice. Over time, recordings are reintroduced in new formats, distributed through new channels, or licensed to new partners. In many of these cases, the original documentation or internal know-how about earlier releases is no longer readily available. The person or team that registered the recording under a previous sales configuration may no longer be involved, or the historical records may be incomplete.

At the same time, modern digital distribution systems require every release to carry a globally recognised commercial identifier, such as a North American UPC or a European EAN barcode, regardless of whether the release is physical or digital. This identifier is attached to the **release**, not to the underlying sound recording. When a catalogue is

migrated, re-released, or introduced to a new market, the immediate operational priority is to make the music available for sale on current platforms.

In principle, a re-release of an existing recording should retain the original recording identifier. In practice, when the provenance chain is broken or uncertain, it is often simpler to assign a new ISRC than to reconstruct or recover an older one. Issuing a new ISRC is quick and effectively costless, whereas tracing historical identifiers across systems, distributors, and legacy catalogues can be time-consuming and expensive.

This issue is particularly pronounced in **middle- and lower-income music markets**. In Slovakia and Hungary, surveys conducted in the late 2010s showed that the majority of artists did not work with established record labels. Many artists self-released their recordings, or relied on talent managers who also handled recording and distribution tasks. Even when artists were signed, they were often associated with very small “micro-labels” that did not have dedicated staff for catalogue management or documentation.

Under these conditions, documentation practices are shaped by economic reality. Smaller markets generate lower overall revenues, which limits the resources available for long-term catalogue maintenance, metadata reconciliation, and identifier management. At the same time, labels and artist-led operations in these markets tend to have **low survival rates**: entities dissolve, people move on, and institutional memory is lost. When documentation breaks down, identifiers are more likely to be mismatched, duplicated, or forgotten.

This creates a **self-reinforcing cycle**. Lower revenues lead to weaker documentation capacity; weaker documentation leads to lost or misallocated revenues; and lost revenues further reduce the ability to invest in proper catalogue management. Notably, this cycle is most visible in the same markets where we also observe substantially lower per-unit prices in recorded music.

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As a result, the same sound recording may legitimately appear under multiple ISRCs over its lifetime. This reflects the operational realities of catalogue management in fragmented and resource-constrained markets, rather than any single error or failure. For analytical purposes, however, it means that identifier-based sampling and aggregation are particularly challenging in exactly those markets where price levels are lowest and transparency is most needed.

Dialling proprietary platform identifiers (such as platform-specific track IDs) would in principle avoid this problem, as these identifiers are unique and stable. However, they are proprietary and platform-specific, and therefore unsuitable for cross-platform market analysis. At best, they would allow monitoring of a single service, rather than the market as a whole. For this reason, the experimental dial-sampling dataset is released primarily as a methodological resource, rather than as a basis for valuation.

These limitations led us to a different strategy: instead of attempting to sample the global market directly, we focused on **constructing and maintaining structured catalogue registers** as population frames. As a feasibility exercise and conceptual template, we developed a near-complete Livonian music database, alongside more comprehensive Slovak and Hungarian registers. These efforts revealed a further structural issue: no actor has a complete view of their “own” repertoire. Livonian culture is dispersed across several countries, and in the Slovak case, a substantial share of recordings associated with Slovak artists are registered abroad, outside the Slovak ISRC registrar and often beyond the visibility of national rights management organisations. Our work in these cases therefore concentrated on identifying works and recordings across borders, and on detecting duplicate identifiers where possible.

These register-based datasets are continuously updated in open knowledge graphs and are primarily used, at this stage, to study questions of circulation, diversity, and exclusion rather than valuation. They demonstrate the feasibility of defining population frames, but they do not in themselves resolve the problem of volume measurement.

Taken together, these experiments underline two points. First, even before turning to quantities, **price levels and exchange rate effects remain insufficiently analysed**, despite their decisive role in shaping observed revenues. Second, the statistically valid observation of volumes is inherently difficult in music markets. Usage distributions are highly skewed, medians are often zero over short accounting periods, and even peer-group comparisons can be distorted by territorial price differences and currency effects. As the price analysis already suggests, an artist’s financial performance may be driven more by geography and exchange rates than by popularity indicators such as follower counts.

For these reasons, the present work deliberately stops at the description of prices and their dispersion. The discussion of volumes is limited to illustrating methodological constraints and possible analytical routes, rather than producing volume estimates. The aim is to show that **price transparency is a necessary precondition** for any meaningful analysis of revenues or quantities, and that without first understanding prices and exchange rates, revenue and volume comparisons risk being misleading.

References

- Antal, Daniel, Fabio Vieira, and Anna Márta Mester. 2025. “Open Music Europe Recorded Music Datasets.” Open Music Observatory. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17985665>.
- BITSS. 2019. “Guidelines for Open Policy Analysis.” Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences. <http://www.bitss.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/OPA-Guidelines.pdf>.
- J, Wilson. 2015. *Evidence-Based Policy Making in the European Commission*. Edited by Elisabeth Lannoo. CIC Report 7440. Oslo (Norway): CICERO Centre for International Climate; Environmental Research. <http://www.cicero.uio.no/en/posts/news/report-from-science-to-policy-how-to-improve-the-dialogue/>.

- Kitzes, Justin, Daniel Turek, and Fatma Deniz, eds. 2018. *The Practice of Reproducible Research: Case Studies and Lessons from the Data-Intensive Sciences*. 1st ed. University of California Press. <http://www.practicereproducibleresearch.org/>.
- Open Music Europe. 2023. “Open Music Europe (OpenMusE) – An Open, Scalable, Data-to-Policy Pipeline for European Music Ecosystems.” <https://doi.org/10.3030/101095295>.